

D2.9

Presence of antibiotics and related veterinary products in olive groves

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Deliverable 2.9 Presence of antibiotics and related veterinary products in olive groves

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Executive Summary

D2.9 is the deliverable for task 2.5 “Assessment of antibiotics and other veterinary drug residues in olive grove soils”. This document describes the status of the different olive groves in terms of antibiotics presence. These pharmacological active substances may end up in the soil as a result of organic fertilization with manure, the use of ovine cattle for weed control, or diffuse soil pollution. Their identification and quantification may contribute to the development of programs for soil restoration, which, in the end, turn into the prevention of toxicological hazards or bacterial antibiotic resistance.

The selected antibiotics for the study are distributed in nine families: diaminopyrimidines, quinolones, ionophores, β -lactams, macrolides, sulphonamides, tetracyclines, amphenicols, and cephalosporins. In total, 51 different antibiotics were chosen as target compounds in the analysis of the olive grove soils. The analytical methodology comprised an ultrasound assisted extraction of the soil samples followed by purification by solid-phase extraction. The antibiotic profile of each sample was determined using Ultra-High Pressure Liquid Chromatography coupled with a triple quadrupole mass spectrometer.

Samples from three different types of olive cultivation were collected: traditional (TD), high-density (HD), and organic (ORG) orchards. Out of the 52 selected olive orchards for Soil O-live project, soil samples were received from 49 different olive orchards from Spain, Greece, Portugal, Morocco and Italy. Different antibiotic profiles were observed from the three types of soil management studied; also, antibiotic profile changes between countries. Despite the high frequency of detection of antibiotic residues, the detected concentrations were in all cases relatively low, below 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$ in most cases.

Comparing the relative detection frequency (Rf) calculated for the nine families of antibiotics in traditionally managed soils, some differences can be observed between countries. In Moroccan samples, tetracyclines and ionophores are more detected than in other countries. β -lactams are detected at a similar rate in Portugal, Spain, and Morocco, and less frequently in Italy. Quinolones are similarly detected in all countries. In HD soils, the single Moroccan sample was free of antibiotics. Greek, Spanish and Portuguese samples showed a similar relative frequency of detection for β -lactams and quinolones. Tetracyclines were detected across these three countries more frequently in Greece. Ionophores were detected in Spain and Greece, while cephalosporins were detected only in Greece. The ORG orchards contained the widest variety of antibiotics among the studied types of soil management, with several target compounds detected across different countries. Quinolones were found in Morocco, Italy, Greece, and Spain. β -lactams had similar relative detection frequency in Portugal and Spain, while Greece had the lowest among them. Sulfonamides were most prevalent in Greece. Tetracyclines had a high relative frequency of detection in Spain followed by Morocco, and similar presence was detected in Italy and Greece. Macrolides were detected only in Spain, with five different macrolides found in 6 samples.

The study on antibiotic dispersion into soil revealed that concentrations generally decrease with depth (10-20 cm compared to 0-10 cm), although the frequency of detection may remain consistent in some cases. Variations were observed between countries and types of soil management.

Table of Acronyms

AB (s) – Antibiotic (s)

ES – Spain

EU – European Union

GR – Greece

HD – High-density

IS – Internal Standard

IT – Italy

MR – Morocco

MS – Mass spectrometry

MS/MS – tandem mass spectrometry

ORG - Organic

PT – Portugal

Rf – Relative frequency of detection

SPE – Solid phase extraction

TD – Traditional

UHPLC – Ultra-High Pressure Liquid Chromatography

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This document aims to disclose the outcomes derived from the evaluation of antibiotics and associated veterinary compounds within designated orchards. The investigation encompassed three distinct soil types: traditional, high-density, and organic groves. The multiresidue method was carried out following the *Standard Operating Procedure D2.6 Multiresidue method for the determination of antibiotics in soils*. The objective of this study is to furnish insights into the various antibiotic families existing in diverse soils, contributing to an enhanced understanding of the prevalence of antibiotics in soil environments.

1.2 Sampling

Samples from the following orchards were received from Spain, Portugal, Morocco, Italy and Greece. The type of crops was three: Traditional (TD), High Density (HD), and Organic (ORG).

Table 1. List of olive orchards from which soil samples were received.

Traditional	High-density	Organic
ES-TD1	ES-HD2	ES-ORG11
ES-TD15	ES-HD22	ES-ORG12
ES-TD5	ES-HD3	ES-ORG13
ES-TD7	ES-HD40	ES-ORG14
ES-TD9	ES-HD8	ES-ORG4
GR-TD30	GR-HD43	ES-ORG6
GR-TD31	MR-HD25	GR-ORG32
GR-TD35	PT-HD51	GR-ORG33
GR-TD36	PT-HD52	GR-ORG34
GR-TD37	PT-HD53	GR-ORG38
GR-TD44		GR-ORG39
GR-TD46		GR-ORG45
IT-TD16*		GR-ORG47
IT-TD20*		IT-ORG17*
IT-TD21**		IT-ORG18*
IT-TD50*		IT-ORG19*
MR-TD24		IT-ORG48**
MR-TD26		IT-ORG49**
MR-TD27		MR-ORG23
MR-TD28		PT-ORG42***
MR-TD29		
PT-TD41		

*Only 3 sampling points were received from these orchards

**Not received

*** Due to a mislabelling the sample in the previous version of this document was classified as PT-TD-42.

From each orchard, 10 different sampling points were received, 5 of them corresponding to 0-10 cm horizon and 5 to the 10-20 cm horizon.

A total of 475 sub-samples were analyzed following the methodology described in the Standard Operating Procedure D2.6 Multiresidue method for the determination of antibiotics in soils. Five sampling points were taken from each orchard: one from the center and four from 2 meters away in each direction, forming a cross. Sub-samples were collected at two depths: 0-10 cm and 10-20 cm; thus 5 sub-samples were obtained at each depth. Each sub-sample was analyzed individually and average values were calculated at each depth, making a total of 49 samples per depth.

2. Experimental

To isolate and determine the antibiotics from soils a solid liquid extraction assisted by ultrasounds followed by solid-phase extraction (SPE) to extract and clean-up the analytes followed by their determination by Ultra-High Pressure Liquid Chromatography (UHPLC) coupled to a triple quadrupole mass spectrometer (MS/MS). The detailed procedure can be found in the deliverable D2.6.

2.1 Multiresidue Analysis for antibiotics in soils

The presence of antibiotics in soil samples was determined by performing a solid-liquid extraction assisted by ultrasounds as a first step. 10 mL of extractant composed by McIlvaine buffer (pH 3.2) with methanol (1:1) were added to 1 g of soil sample, and the mixture was sonicated in an ultrasound bath for 10 min. Afterwards, the extract was diluted to reduce the organic solvent content below 5 % and then the sample was passed through a SPE cartridge, retaining the analytes onto the sorbent material and the matrix being discharged. Finally, the analytes retained were eluted from the cartridge using 5 mL of methanol.

The antibiotic profile of each sample was determined using UHPLC-MS/MS. The Ultimate 3000 UHPLC (Thermo Fisher Scientific), equipped with a Zorbax Eclipse plus C18 column (4.6 x 100 mm, 1.8 µm particle size, Agilent Technologies), operated at a flow rate of 0.4 mL/min. The column was equilibrated with a water:methanol mixture (95:5). Detection followed the optimal parameters for each analyte, obtained through their individual infusion into the mass spectrometer (details are given in deliverable D2.6).

The methodology provided the following analytical properties:

Table 2. Analytical characteristics

Recoveries	40-108 %
Precision (RSD)	6-18 %
Linear range	0.05 – 500 µg/kg
98% of compounds have LoQ < 10 µg/kg	

The analyzed antibiotics were the following:

Table 3. Analysed antibiotics

Family	Compound
Diaminopyrimidines	Trimethoprim
	Trimethoprim-d9 (IS)*
Quinolones	Ciprofloxacin
	Difloxacin
	Orbifloxacin
	Enrofloxacin-d5 (IS)*
	Enrofloxacin
	Norfloxacin
	Ofloxacin
	Lomefloxacin
	Enoxacin
	Danofloxacin
	Levofloxacin
	Marbofloxacin
	Fleroxacin
	Sarafloxacin hydrochloride
	Flumequine
Ionophores	Monensin
	Monensin methylester
β-lactam	Amoxicillin trihydrate
	Amoxicillin
	Cephapirin
	Cefuroxime
	Penicillin-G
	Penicillin-V
	Oxacillin
	Dicloxacillin
	Dicloxacillin sodium monohydrate
	Cefotaxime
	Ampicillin
Macrolides	Azithromycin
	Clarithromycin
	Erythromycin
	Spiramycin
	Tylosin
Sulfonamides	Sulfachloropyridazine
	Sulfadiazine
	Sulfadimethoxyn
	Sulfadoxine
	Sulfamethoxazole
	13C6-sulfamethoxazole (IS)*
	Sulfamonomethoxine
	Sulfathiazole
	Sulfapyridine
	Sulfasoxazole
Amprolium	
Tetracyclines	Sulfamethazine
	Chlortetracycline
	Doxycycline
	Tetracycline hydrochloride
	Oxytetracycline
Amphenicols	Metacycline hydrochloride
	Florfenicol
Cefalosporin	Florfenicol-d3 (IS)*
	Cefazolin

*IS: Internal Standard

3. Results

Soil O-live selected 52 orchards as sampling locations, categorized into three groups based on soil management: traditional (TD) (22 orchards), high-density (HD) (12 orchards), and organic (ORG) (19 orchards). These orchards were located across five countries: Spain (16 orchards), Greece (15 orchards), Italy (9 orchards), Morocco (7 orchards), and Portugal (5 orchards). Nevertheless, although soils from 52 locations were expected, only 49 orchards were sampled due to logistical and climatic challenges. Despite this, the collected samples offer a diverse representation of soil management types and countries, providing valuable insights into contamination levels across various sites.

Ten soil sub-samples were taken from each orchard, as detailed in section 1.2: 5 sub-samples were collected at depth 0-10 cm (H1) and other 5 sub-samples were collected at depth 10-20 cm (H2). Average results are provided for each soil depth, after the individual analysis by LC-MS/MS of each sub-sample.

3.1 Antibiotic assessment by soil management type

Samples were analysed for the presence of 51 antibiotics (ABs) belonging to nine antibiotic families (see detailed information in Table 3): diaminopyrimidines (1 AB), quinolones (14 ABs), ionophores (2 ABs), β -lactams (10 ABs), macrolides (5 ABs), sulphonamides (11 ABs), tetracyclines (5 ABs), amphenicols (1 AB), and cephalosporins (1 AB).

To make a comparison of the presence of antibiotics between the different countries and types of soil management, the relative frequency of detection (Rf) has been calculated, which considers the number of samples from each country, the number of antibiotics analysed for each family, and the positives detected in each sample group. This gives us a better picture of the actual frequency of detection, considering that we do not have the same number of samples between countries or between the different types of soil management.

$$Rf = \frac{\text{Total positives per family}}{N^{\circ} \text{ of samples per country} \cdot N^{\circ} \text{ compounds per family}} \cdot 100$$

3.1.1 Traditional managed orchards

Different antibiotics profiles were observed between countries for the traditional managed orchard selected. The complete results are listed in Table 4. Up to five different families of antibiotics were detected in the different countries, being Morocco the country with more compounds detected compared to the other.

Figure 1. Relative frequency of detection (%) of each family of antibiotics per country in soil samples from TD managed olive orchards

As depicted in Figure 1, tetracyclines in TD soils were only detected in soils from Morocco. Two different tetracyclines were detected four times, resulting in a relative frequency of detection (Rf) of 20%. Quinolones were detected across all countries, with Spain and Portugal showing similar Rf values of 7.1%. Slightly lower values were observed in Italy and Greece, with Rf values of 2.4% and 4.1%, respectively. In Morocco, the Rf for quinolones was 10%, with two quinolones detected seven times. For β -lactams, the Rf was 30% in Portugal, 22% in Spain (with three different β -lactams detected 11 times), and 16% in Morocco. Lower Rf values were observed in Italy and Greece. Notably, the relative frequency of detection for ionophores was 50% in Portugal and 40% in Morocco. Despite these calculated Rf values, the concentrations detected across all soil samples were below 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$.

Table 4. Individual antibiotics, number of positives detected and relative frequency by family at 0-10 cm depth per country in TD orchards.

AB groups (No of compounds)		TD														
		MR (n=5)			IT (n=3)			GR (n=7)			ES (n=5)			PT (n=1)		
		Individually detected ABs	No of positives	Rel. Freq. /Fam (%)*												
Diaminopyrimidines	(1)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Quinolones	(14)	2	7	10.0	1	1	2.4	2	4	4.1	1	5	7.1	1	1	7.1
Ionophores	(2)	1	4	40.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	50.0
B-Lactams	(10)	2	8	16.0	2	2	6.7	1	5	7.1	3	11	22.0	3	3	30.0
Macrolides	(5)	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	3	8.6	-	-	-	-	-	-
Sulfonamides	(11)	5	8	14.5	1	3	3.0	1	3	3.9	2	3	5.5	-	-	-
Tetracyclines	(5)	2	4	16.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Amphenicols	(1)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cephalosporin	(1)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

*The relative frequency of detection per family is calculated based on the number of total elements (compounds per family and total number of samples per country) in relation to the total of positives detected in each family.

3.1.2 High-density managed orchards

For HD orchards a lower number of samples were analysed, the complete data is listed in Table 5. It is worth highlighting the absence of antibiotics in the Moroccan sample. In the case of Greek samples, the detected antibiotics presented different Rf. Tetracyclines a 40 % of relative frequency of detection, higher than the detected in Spain (8 %) and Portugal (13.3 %). β -lactams presented a similar pattern across Greece, Spain, and Portugal in the span of 20 to 24 % as can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Relative frequency of detection (%) of each family of antibiotics per country in soil samples from HD managed olive orchards

Quinolones were also detected in these three countries, with varying Rf values, ranging from 22.9% in Spain to 7.1% in the Greek samples. Ionophores were detected in both Spanish and Portuguese samples, with a Rf of 60% in Spain and 16.7% in Portugal. Lastly, cephalosporins were detected in the Greek sample, making a 100 % of Rf. As stated previously, the detected concentrations are always at trace level, even a diverse variety of antibiotics are found.

Table 5. Individual antibiotics, number of positives detected and relative frequency by family at 0-10 cm depth per country in HD orchards.

AB groups (No of compounds)		HD											
		MR (n=1)			GR (n=1)			ES (n=5)			PT (n=3)		
		Individually detected ABs	No of positives	Rel. Freq. (%)*	Individually detected ABs	No of positives	Rel. Freq. (%)*	Individually detected ABs	No of positives	Rel. Freq. (%)*	Individually detected ABs	No of positives	Rel. Freq. (%)*
Diaminopyrimidines	(1)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Quinolones	(14)	-	-	-	1	1	7.1	8	16	22.9	5	5	11.9
Ionophores	(2)	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	6	60.0	1	1	16.7
B-Lactam	(10)	-	-	-	2	2	20.0	4	12	24.0	3	7	23.3
Macrolides	(5)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Sulfonamides	(11)	-	-	-	2	2	18.2	1	3	5.5	1	1	3.0
Tetracyclines	(5)	-	-	-	2	2	40.0	1	2	8.0	1	2	13.3
Amphenicols	(1)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cephalosporin	(1)	-	-	-	1	1	100	-	-	-	-	-	-

*The relative frequency of detection per family is calculated based on the number of total elements (compounds per family and total number of samples per country) in relation to the total of positives detected in each family.

3.1.3 Organic managed orchards

As expected, the organic managed orchards presented the most and diverse number of samples and compounds detected due to the nature of this kind of agriculture. Table 6 shows the complete results for ORG samples.

Figure 3. Relative frequency of detection (%) of each family of antibiotics per country in soil samples from ORG managed olive orchards

Different families of AB as quinolones, β -lactams, sulfonamides and tetracyclines were detected across different countries and samples as can be seen in Figure 3. Quinolones were detected in samples from Morocco and Italy with a Rf of 7.1 %, Greece (12.2 %) and Spain with a Rf of 18.6 %, the higher among all the countries, even though is a low value in terms of frequency. In Portugal and Spain, β -lactams were detected at a similar Rf, 30 – 32 %, for Italy and Morocco the obtained relative frequency detection was 20 %, in the case of Greek samples this value drops to 12.9 %. For sulfonamides, the higher Rf was detected in Greece, with a 16.9 %, the other countries ranged from 9.1 to 12.7 %. In the case of tetracyclines, in Italian and Greek samples the Rf was similar, 16.7 and 17.9 %, respectively. For Moroccan samples, this Rf was 25 % while for the Spanish samples this Rf rose up to 45 %. Macrolides were detected in Spanish samples, 5 different macrolides were observed 6 times, making a 24 % of relative detection rate.

Table 6. Individual antibiotics, number of positives detected and relative frequency by family at 0-10 cm depth per country in ORG orchards.

AB groups (No of compounds)	ORG														
	MR (n=1)			IT (n=3)			GR (n=7)			ES (n=6)			PT (n=1)		
	Individually detected ABs	No of positives	Rel. Freq. (%) [*]	Individually detected ABs	No of positives	Rel. Freq. (%) [*]	Individually detected ABs	No of positives	Rel. Freq. (%) [*]	Individually detected ABs	No of positives	Rel. Freq. (%) [*]	Individually detected ABs	No of positives	Rel. Freq. (%) [*]
Diaminopyrimidines (1)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Quinolones (14)	1	1	7.1	2	3	7.14	2	12	12.2	4	13	18.6	-	-	-
Ionophores (2)	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	7.1	1	1	10.0	2	2	100
B-Lactam (10)	2	2	20.0	3	6	20.0	3	9	12.9	4	16	32.0	3	3	30.0
Macrolides (5)	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	2.9	5	6	24.0	-	-	-
Sulfonamides (11)	1	1	9.1	2	4	12.1	4	13	16.9	3	7	12.7	-	-	-
Tetracyclines (5)	1	1	20.0	2	2	13.3	3	5	14.3	4	9	30.0	-	-	-
Amphenicols (1)	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Cephalosporin (1)	1	1	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

^{*}The relative frequency of detection per family is calculated based on the number of total elements (compounds per family and total number of samples per country) in relation to the total of positives detected in each family.

3.2 Antibiotic dispersion in soils

To investigate the diffusion of antibiotics through soil, samples were collected at a greater depth (10-20 cm) from the same locations spots as the initial sampling (0-10 cm). All the data is displayed in Table 7.

Generally, antibiotic concentrations were lower at 10-20 cm depth compared to 0-10 cm. However, in some cases, the relative frequency of detection remained consistent. In the Moroccan samples, the relative frequency of detection of the target compounds was nearly identical for TD and ORG orchards. In contrast, for HD orchards, some compound families were detected for the first time, with relative frequencies ranging from 7.1% for quinolones to 27.3% for sulfonamides. For the Italian orchards, no significant changes were observed in terms of detection, a similar pattern was noted in Greece, except for the HD sample, where ionophores were detected at a relative frequency of 50%. In the Spanish samples, some values decreased while others increased, such as tetracyclines in HD soils. Finally, the Portuguese samples showed similar behaviour at both 10-20 cm and 0-10 cm depths.

Figure 4 describe the antibiotics detected across the three soil management types. The percentages reflect the depth at which the antibiotic was most frequently detected relative to the total number of positive samples.

For soil samples under TD management, most detected compounds are in the 0–10 cm layer. In this case, no clear trend is observed for any specific antibiotic family regarding their preferred depth, as all generally accumulate in the most superficial soil layer. Only two compounds, sulfachloropyridazine and flumequine, were exclusively detected in the 10–20 cm layer. Some compounds, such as amoxicillin, show a similar presence in both soil layers, with detection percentages around 50%. This behaviour could be attributed to its polarity and high solubility in water, which allows it to move more easily between different soil layers.

In the case of soil samples from HD orchards, antibiotics appear to be more evenly distributed between the two analysed soil layers. There is no clear trend indicating a preference for accumulation in the more superficial layer (0–10 cm) or the deeper layer (10–20 cm). This distribution may be due to the more intensive soil management practices typical of these farms.

For instance, the detected quinolones show very similar percentages between both soil layers. In some cases, they are slightly more prevalent in the 0–10 cm layer, but in many others, they are either equally present in both layers or predominantly found in the deeper layer. This suggests that such soils are actively worked, likely mixing through mechanical cultivation practices. This is particularly relevant as quinolones have low mobility in soils, tending to remain retained in the soil matrix and not naturally penetrating deeper layers on their own.

The antibiotics detected in the ORG type samples showed a higher prevalence in the more superficial soil layer. In this case, 13 out of the 24 detected antibiotics were exclusively present in the 0–10 cm layer. This could be attributed to the application of organic fertilizers, which are deposited on the soil surface. Only three antibiotics were detected with a greater prevalence in the 10–20 cm layer, while the remaining eight were found at varying percentages in both soil layers. Quinolones exhibit low mobility in soil due to their strong adsorption to the soil matrix, preventing them from naturally penetrating deeper layers. In these samples, quinolones such as levofloxacin were found in the upper soil layer, while others like enrofloxacin were detected in the deeper layers. This may result from the continuous application of organic fertilizers, which progressively become buried beneath newer layers. Consequently, previously deposited

compounds are pushed downward, suggesting that their movement is driven more by mechanical and/or physical processes rather than chemical factors.

Table 7. Relative frequency by family at 0-20 cm per country.

AB groups (No of compounds)		Rel. Freq. /Fam (%)*														
		MR (n=7)			IT (n=6)			GR (n=15)			ES (n=17)			PT (n=5)		
		TD (n=5)	HD (n=1)	ORG (n=1)	TD (n=3)	HD	ORG (n=3)	TD (n=7)	HD (n=1)	ORG (n=7)	TD (n=5)	HD (n=5)	ORG (n=6)	TD (n=1)	HD (n=3)	ORG (n=1)
Diaminopyrimidines	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Quinolones	14	11.4	7.1	14.3	4.8	7.1	8.2	-	12.8	4.3	11.4	12.9	14.3	9.5	7.1	
Ionophores	2	10.0	-	-	-	-	14.3	50.0	-	40.0	-	-	50.0	-	-	
B-Lactam	10	16.0	20.0	20.0	6.7	13.3	2.9	20.0	18.0	16.0	12.0	18.0	20.0	20.0	30.0	
Macrolides	5	4.0	-	-	6.7	-	8.6	-	24.0	-	-	24.0	-	-	-	
Sulfonamides	11	-	27.3	18.2	3.0	12.1	-	27.3	5.5	-	1.8	5.5	-	3.0	-	
Tetracyclines	5	-	25.0	25.0	-	8.3	-	50.0	50.0	-	30.0	50.0	-	25.0	-	
Amphenicols	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
Cephalosporin	1	-	-	100	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	

*The relative frequency of detection per family is calculated based on the number of total elements (compounds per family and total number of samples per country) in relation to the total of positives detected in each family.

Fig. 4. Antibiotic dispersion in TD orchards by compound (% over total positives)

Fig. 5. Antibiotic dispersion in HD orchards by compound (% over total positives)

Fig. 6. Antibiotic dispersion in ORG orchards by compound (% over total positives)

4. Discussion

A total of 475 samples were analysed under the conditions of the *Multiresidue method for the determination of antibiotics in soils (D2.6)*. These samples originated from three different types of olive grove cultivation: traditional, high-density, and organic. The samples were collected from various orchards at two depths (or horizons): 0-10 cm and 10-20 cm, with 5 sampling points, resulting in 10 samples per orchard. The five sub-samples have been combined to obtain homogenized and robust results, and a final sample was obtained for each depth. Although 52 samples were expected from each depth, logistical and climatic challenges resulted in 49 samples per depth.

Different soil management practices showed distinct antibiotic contamination profiles between countries and types of soil management. Noting that even there are some cases that the relative frequency of detection is high, that does not mean that the concentrations detected are high. Even though antibiotics are detected frequently in soils their concentrations are not over the limit for other compounds like pesticides to compare, as there is not regulation at this point for antibiotics.

Comparing the relative frequency of detection of the nine different families of antibiotics in TD soils there are differences between the different families and their detection rate. In Morocco tetracyclines and ionophores are detected more frequently than in the rest of the countries. β -lactams are detected in a similar rate in Portugal, Spain, and Morocco and less frequently detected in Italy. Quinolones are detected in all the countries with similar relative frequency of detection. In HD soils the sample from Morocco was free of target compounds. The samples from Greece, Spain and Portugal presented a relative frequency of detection (Rf) similar for β -lactams, about 20 %, quinolones were also detected with a Rf from 7.1 to 22.9 %, tetracyclines were detected across these three countries, being more frequently detected in Greece. Ionophores were detected in Spain and Greece, while cephalosporins were detected in Greece. The ORG orchards exhibited the most varied range of antibiotic residues, with several classes detected across different countries. Quinolones were found in Morocco, Italy, Greece, and Spain, with Spain showing the Rf at 18.6%. β -lactams had similar Rf values in Portugal and Spain (30-32%), while Greece had the lowest at 12.9%. Sulfonamides were most prevalent in Greece (16.9%), with other countries ranging from 9.1% to 12.7%. Tetracyclines had a high Rf in Spain (30%), followed by Morocco (20%), and similar Rf values in Italy (13.3%) and Greece (14.3%). Macrolides were detected only in Spain, with five different macrolides found in 6 instances, yielding a 24% detection rate.

The investigation into the movement of antibiotics in soil revealed that concentrations generally decrease with depth (10-20 cm compared to 0-10 cm), although the frequency of detection may remain consistent in some cases. Variations were observed between countries and types of soil management (TD, HD, and ORG). In general, compounds tended to accumulate in the surface layer (0-10 cm) in TD and ORG soils, with some exceptions such as sulfachloropyridazine and flumequine, which were exclusively found in the 10-20 cm layer in TD soils. In HD soils, antibiotics were more evenly distributed between both layers, likely due to more intensive management practices such as tillage. The presence of quinolones in deeper layers, despite their

low mobility, suggests that the movement of these compounds may be influenced by mechanical or physical processes rather than chemical ones, especially in HD and ORG soils where organic fertilizers are applied. Amoxicillin, due to its high solubility, showed similar presence in both layers in TD soils.